

Why Nothing Exists

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Introduction and Empty Space

“Nothing” cannot exist. For if it did, its very existence would turn it into something. Nothingness therefore can’t be “an absence of existence” but rather just “something that exists” and is *called* “nothing”. It has to be nothing in name only.

This conception of “nothing” can be understood using the example of empty space. Empty space is said to be empty because it contains “nothing”. However, even the “emptiness” that empty space contains in of itself is still “something that exists”. Therefore when empty space is said to be empty this does not mean that it actually contains “nothing that exists” but rather that it contains emptiness or just a *something called nothing* within it. This nothing would have to be a thing that exists since it does in fact make up parts of space.

Does Empty Space or “Physical Nothingness” Even Exist?

Now in truth even a physical vacuum isn’t claimed to be empty. Per the Standard Model of Particle Physics, all of space itself is filled with “quantum fields” that fluctuate and themselves contain energy. It is the excitations of these “fields” at certain thresholds that constitute “subatomic particles”. Therefore according to this, “physical emptiness” does not actually contain “nothing” but rather quantum fields that themselves act as the “potentials for things to exist” i.e. subatomic particles. However, when these quantum fields are not sufficiently excited and don’t cause “discrete particles”, it can be said that the space in which they exist seems *tangibly* empty. This is not because that space contains “nothing that is real” but rather because it contains “no discrete particles” but only the fields that have the potential to result in them. Such discrete particles would be formed only when these fields are excited by probabilistic fluctuations. These fields alone however don’t result in any *tangible* things that exist and therefore give the illusion of empty space.

The reason that such space may appear “empty” is because at first glance it seems as if quantum fields alone do not contain any “individual entities” within them. However, once the mechanisms of how they work in producing real and virtual particles is discovered, said space could not really be considered as truly empty since the “potential” for individual particles is always present and the actual fields themselves can be considered “things”.

Now if even empty space does not contain “nothingness” but rather quantum fields, is physical nothingness even real? Or rather is the entirety of everything just “quantum fields” fluctuating into particles and virtual particles?

Perhaps the only way to conceive of nothing is therefore not as something that doesn’t exist but rather as something that does exist but cannot be “individually understood as a thing”. Nothing in this way wouldn’t be *nothing* but rather “no-thing” with thing here being a discrete individual entity that can be understood.

What Does it Mean to be a Thing?

Now of course, this is semantically ambiguous. After all, what is a “thing anyway? Isn’t a “thing” just a word for an entity that exists? Well perhaps the word “thing” doesn’t signify something that exists but rather something that exists *individually*. A thing therefore would be something that is individually “measurable” and itself contains information that could be “found out”. For example, subatomic particles are individually “measurable” because they alone have properties such as spin, charge and mass that describe them. In this way each subatomic particle is essentially just a container for “bits of information” that itself are potentially “discoverable” to an observer. It is this property of having discoverable information that essentially allows these particles to be recognized as individual discrete “things” separate from their environments.

Now the reason that quantum fields alone may therefore “seem” like they are “nothing” is because at first glance it seems as if they are not in any way individually distinguishable from their environments. However, once it is discovered that there are different quantum fields that produce different types of subatomic particles, it can then be concluded that such fields themselves are actually individual “things” that are different from one another and therefore each have “individual information”.

Why Must Things Be Measurable?

The reason that things need to have “individually discoverable information” to tangibly exist is because the only way in which anything can be measured or discovered in the first place is through the perceptual and processing abilities of the human brain. For when quantum particles are “discovered” they are not “seen” but rather have their properties “discovered” through the measurement of larger interactions or analysis of data. The human brain is capable of integrating this information and concluding that it implies the presence of a particle with discrete properties. Therefore all of these particles are only individually discovered because of their distinct properties that take the form of “measurable information” in the human brain.

Since the universe and “things” within it are only known to exist to humans from the perspectives of humans, then the definition of what constitutes “things” are intimately dependent on what the human brain is capable of processing. Since the human brain is able to learn that “things” are individual entities separate from their environment when they have information that differs them from their environment it is clear how “discoverable information” is a necessary qualifier in defining a tangible individual “thing”. However, obviously things that don’t have “discoverable information” may still theoretically exist, however wouldn’t be known to the human brain since the human brain only “learns” things are “individual things” based on the differing information they contain. This is because the human brain is essentially a processor that processes “relevant information” based off of centuries of evolutionary molding. However, what the human brain registers as being “significant” about something is not actually the true nature of the “something”. Instead it is what is evolutionary important. Therefore, the human brain has been trained to register the different “informations” of things as being important. However the true nature of the “informational inputs” that are processed by the brain are actually unknown. All that is known about them is the “discoverable information” they convey.

It is this discoverable information that allows the brain to “group” and “schematize” things as individual things apart from their overlaying environments. It is that “schematization” that allows for the definition of “things” as being distinguishable from other things when in reality all these things are only informational inputs to the brain.

For example, take a blade of grass. A blade of grass can be “seen” or “felt” when in reality both the image and feeling of grass are just products of the brain translating informational input. While the brain is capable of schematizing certain informational inputs as “grass”, the actual nature of the input to the brain that is translated as “grass” can never be known. This is because the brain itself is biased in how it demonstrates the products of the universe to its subject. It does not show the subject “what is actually there” but rather “what is useful to see” based on millennia of evolutionary processes that molded its “filtering” abilities. Therefore the only thing that can be known about these “inputs” is that they contain information since that is what the brain essentially uses to translate individual things.

What Causes “Things” To Have Information in the first place?

Now sure the brain may “perceive” individual things based off of their information, but what is it that causes these things to have information that separates them from other things in the first place? If they are just inputs then what is it that allows them to “have information for brains to even process”? To explain, subatomic particles and even quantum fields in general must still have “mechanisms” behind the information they convey. For what is it in the first place that gives particles properties such as “charge”, “spin” and even “position”? Even a physical theory of everything that perfectly describes how such properties are explained by the interactions and mathematical makeups of different fields would eventually need to explain what underlies such fields at their cores. This is to say that anything individually “discoverable” at all in such a “theory of everything” would only be discoverable because it has discoverable information and that discoverable information which separates it from its environment must itself have a reason for having that information.

Therefore “discoverable information” must have its own mechanism for “existing” that presumably also contains information and requires a mechanism. Therefore, any things that contain information in general can only be reduced to subsets of themselves that also have information associated with them. This is because anything that is separate from anything else in any of its properties must essentially have information that defines it as individual. However, eventually there must come a point where these “particles and fields” are reduced to their most fundamental parts that don’t have individually discoverable information. This is because anything divisible must fundamentally be composed of indivisible entities that themselves wouldn’t contain any information since they wouldn’t be differentiable from their environment. It would then be at this point where perhaps “things” can’t be conceived since they are no longer individually discoverable by the human brain.

To elaborate, the human brain is limited in its processing abilities and is most likely incapable of discovering everything that “has information”. In fact it is this very reason that “quantum fields” themselves are commonly perceived to constitute “emptiness” - because it is misunderstood how anything without “discrete particles” could itself contain “discoverable

individual things”. However if all particles and fields are fundamentally composed of things that at their cores are all unitary and can no longer be distinguished from one another then it could be said that each of these things don’t have “individually measurable information”. Therefore it would not simply be that the human brain is “incapable” of discovering their information but rather that they simply each actually “contain” no information since there would be no different properties that separate one of these fundamental “things” from another.

Can Things Exist Without them Having Information?

Now it is fair to ask how “something that exists” cannot have “measurable information”? Isn’t anything that exists defined as individually existing only because of it having “measurable information”? If something “exists” without such information then how can it be known that it even exists in the first place if its information is unlearnable?

The answer is that the only way that something cannot have “measurable information” and exist is if it is “indistinguishable” from the rest of its environment but still “innately separate”. To explain, the only means by which anything is “measured” is by its having “distinguishable” properties that can be recognized as separate from its environment. If something has no distinguishable properties from anything else then it individually cannot be measured. Now if any individual thing that exists must be composed of “smaller things” that exist then eventually there needs to be at the core of “anything that exists” something indivisible that can no longer be broken down. However, anything that has “individually discoverable information” must also have components that make it up that account for its differentiation from its environment. Anything truly indivisible however cannot have such components. Furthermore, anything truly indivisible must have only one feature - that it exists. Therefore if something’s only property is that of “existence” then such a thing could not be separated from its environment since everything that makes up its environment too consists of indivisible components that only property is “existence”. These indivisible components of “existence” again wouldn’t have any “discoverable information” at all since they have no differing features from one another. Rather they are all the same in their only property which is existence. Therefore underlying everything there must be individual indivisible “particles of existence” that don’t have any information - not because they are undiscoverable due to constraints of the human brain but rather because they are undiscoverable because of their lack of individually identifying properties.

In the 19th century it was assumed that “atoms” fit this description but of course that was until more fundamental subatomic particles were discovered. Furthermore, even subatomic particles have differences between one another (such as mass, charge, spin etc) and are therefore distinguishable from one another. It is that distinguishability that allows them to be measured. The actual “indivisible components” that essentially “make up” all things will never be discovered since they are “undiscoverable” because they lack individually discoverable information. It would be these “individually indivisible undiscoverable” things that would truly be “nothings”. Again, not because they don’t exist but rather because they cannot be “measured” and separated as “individual entities”.

Summary Thus Far

To summarize thus far, everything physical is composed of “subatomic particles” that themselves have distinguishable properties. These distinguishable properties of subatomic particles need to be a result of the differences between their more innate components (these would be differences between the different quantum fields that presumably cause them to exist and their subsequent interactions). However at the heart of anything that exists, there must also be fundamental indivisible components. Truly indivisible components could not be different from one another as they could not contain any differing “information”. This is because “information” only exists when an individual thing is distinguishable from another individual thing. If both things are truly indivisible then they wouldn’t have any “tangible differences” individually and therefore could never be “distinguishably measured”. This is because they would each only have one uniform property - that of existing. Therefore, every single “subatomic entity” in this regard would need to be composed of uniform indivisible fundamental entities that themselves do not individually contain “measurable information”. It are these “immeasurable indivisible” entities that can’t be individually discovered but can still be conceived as “nothings” or “not things”.

An Example of How Nothings Can Make up Anythings

Another way of thinking about this is to imagine a one dimensional line. A one dimensional line can differ from another one dimensional line only in terms of its length and position. On a one dimensional axis for example, line A could be of size 5 and be situated at coordinates 0 through 4. Line B on the other hand could be of size 2 and situated at coordinates 7 through 8. Therefore each of these lines essentially has 2 pieces of information - their size and position. With these 2 pieces of information everything about each of these lines can be known.

The difference between each of their sizes could be explained by there being more components within one of them than the other. For example, the line of size 5 has 5 sized 1 components compared to the 2 sized 1 components in the other line. However, what if one wanted to recuse these lines to their most fundamental components. In order to do so they must continually divide each line until all of their components are indivisible. Now any such finite division of a one dimensional line could always be further divided as there could always be smaller divisions of any finite sized sub-line (since any line of size x where x is nonzero could further be divided by 2). However there must still exist fundamentally indivisible components within both these lines since anything divisible must of course be composed of things that are fundamentally indivisible. Therefore, any fundamental indivisible component of each line must be of size 0 since 0 is the only number that truly indivisible. For only 0 could not be further subdivided. This 0 however wouldn’t “not exist at all” but rather be a physical 0 a la Massimo Melli’s logon that exists only as a 0 dimensional coordinate without size. It is that property of “existence” that allows such a coordinate to make up finite lines. However, this physical 0 would essentially also have “no discoverable information” since it lacks any size and does not take up any space on the one dimensional axis. Their only property would be that of “existence”.

In terms of how many 0’s it would actually take to form these 1 dimensional lines, there must always be an infinite number of 0’s in each line. This is because there is no finite amount of 0 dimensional coordinates that themselves could add up to anything with a true length in one dimension. Any finite line can always be subdivided into more and more 0’s. Therefore, every

finite one dimensional line must be composed of an infinite amount of 0 dimensional coordinates. While such 0 dimensional coordinates wouldn't have any individually differentiating information in the first dimension, they would still need to exist. However, since they all have no size and no actual position (besides for knowing that they're part of the line) in the first dimension, they wouldn't actually be measurable. Rather they would simply be "existing property-less entities". Since they have no size they would all be of size 0 and since they are all of size 0 they would all never actually take up any "position" in the first dimension. Therefore they can only be described as "0" and cannot properly be considered "individually measurable things" since they lack any differentiable information to distinguish them.

To demonstrate this, if infinity can be described as $X/0$ for nonzero values of X (since anything finite that is divided by 0 essentially tends towards infinity), then $X/0 * 0$ or $0/0$ can be used to describe the actual "size" of any finite entity. Such could be seen by setting any number equal to 0. In $2 * 0 = 0$, 2 can be set equal to $0/0$ such as how in $1 * 0 = 0$, 1 can be also set equal to $0/0$. In this way, all finite entities can be shown to be composed of an infinite number of indivisible or "0 sized" entities.

It can be seen here from here how all one dimensional lines are essentially composed of an infinite amount of "0s" or "nothings that exist". Furthermore, since space essentially contains three dimensional entities instead of one dimensional lines, the same logic can be used for anything within space. Everything must essentially be composed of 0's - information-less entities that's only property is that of existence. These would never be individually discoverable because there is a never a way to separate one from another 0 in their environment because they all share the same exact properties. Again, the only way to differentiate individual things is by discovering differing information between these "things" and their environments. Yet such fundamental 0s would all just simply "exist" and have no differing informations from one another. Therefore they would all be "immeasurable" and lack discoverable individual existences.

Using this logic, an infinite number of uniform indivisible "particles" result in "finite particles" that themselves exist with differing properties. Furthermore since these indivisible particles don't have any differences between one another and therefore aren't individually discoverable since they have no differing information from their environments they essentially aren't tangible as individual things but rather only are "no-things" or things without differentiable individual information. Therefore, it can be said that "nothings" do exist and in fact makes up everything that is not nothing exists. In this way it can be said that something did not come from nothing but is still is nothing, just each an infinite amount of nothings.

How are there different finite things if all that underlies them are uniform?

The only question then becomes how any infinite number of "nothings" can actually appear as something? For if everything is composed of the same exact "0s" with no distinguishable information then how are there ever "different things" with information?

Perhaps the key here has to do with contextualization. Every finite "thing" is only a finite thing subjectively. In reality as demonstrated every single finite "thing" is essentially just an objective

infinite configuration of 0s. Out of configurations of 0s however, a finite “thing” can subjectively emerge based on how the combinations of the infinite 0s are configured. This is to say that in reality these “things” are always an infinite configuration of indivisible entities or 0s however to observers they *appear* as being finite sized entities. This is perhaps because there is a differentiation between the “contents” of things and the “contexts” of things.

While objectively there are only “infinite zeros”, there are also “differing ways to look at these 0s”. Sure in terms of conceivability one may imagine a group of 0s and think “if they all have the same properties they can never be distinguished from one another”. However, each of these 0s do have their own existences, just lack the information necessary to be “recognized” as individuals. Yet because they each have an innate property of individual existence they still ontologically do “individually exist”. Therefore even though they are all the same in terms of what is thought of as “differentiable properties” they all still innately separately exist. Therefore configurations of these 0s are still possible just not necessarily “fathomable” to beings who require “information” to understand any differences between separate things.

An example of contextualization

An infinite configuration of 0s can be likened to a sheet of paper. This blank sheet of paper essentially consists of an infinite number of “objective indivisible segments” of white space. However together the entire paper looks like one thing because these “objective indivisible segments” lack any differentiable properties from one another. Therefore the contents or *whiteness* of the paper is seen as “one individual thing” rather than an infinite amount of “individual things” because each indivisible entity within the paper that makes up the paper does not have any information to actually individuate oneself.

However if a box is drawn on the sheet of paper, now there is essentially a “separated” box of whiteness from the rest of the whiteness on the paper. This separated whiteness also fundamentally has an infinite amount of “indivisible entities” just like the entire sheet of paper (this is because any finite things must have an infinite amount of invisible 0s). However, these infinite amount of 0s that make up the box also now have “borders” due to the lines drawn surrounding them. These borders give the box a property of conceivable position that allows it to be contextualized as “one box” rather than just an infinite number of 0s. It is this that gives the box information and allows it to be a tangible individual “thing”. In reality however the contents of this drawn box are still just an infinite amount of 0s objectively. Yet because of the borders around them, they appear as if though they make up something - the box.

Now one could ask - “Yes but in the physical universe where does the ink come from to draw borders that make up finite entities? There may be an infinite number of indivisible fundamental entities yet if there is no ink to draw borders around them that allow them to take on separable information, how can they ever come to finitely exist?”. This is to ask - how are borders drawn amongst infinite zeros in order to create the illusion of separated finite entities?

The answer is that borders do not need “ink” to be drawn at all since they are always conceivable by the “contextualizations” of observers. For if there are an infinite number of 0s, then there are also an infinite number of ways to configure or “look at these 0s”. The process of how these 0s

are looked at will describe how they take on the information that they do. This process however is only possible via contextualization by observers who essentially “provide” the objective infinite 0s a subjective existence. For observers by definition have their own “subjective contexts” which allow these infinite objective 0s to actually be “looked at in different ways”. The observers therefore do not draw border but are “borders” that essentially implicitly contextualize the infinite 0s they conceive.

In my next paper I will further explain how understanding how observers provide contexts to objective “infinite indivisible iotas” actually result in subjective “finite measurable amalgamations” of them.

This shows that infinite “nothings” may always make up “somethings”, but it is them being contextualized by observers that allow these “nothings” to actually ever exist subjectively. In this way “something” is just the subjective manifestation of what is objectively “nothing” and such an objective nothing does in fact exist.